

How 5G Enables Smart Energy: Setup and First Experiences from the NRG-5 Pilots

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Abstract—One of the most challenging application areas for 5G is the smart energy vertical. This includes developing Advanced Metering Infrastructures (AMI), device auto configuration procedures, Demand Response (DR) strategies, and preventive maintenance of the electrical network. The NRG-5 project examines the requirements of the smart energy vertical and develops enabling solutions for the 5G. Results from the project are validated at two test sites over real energy infrastructures (including both electricity and gas equipment). This paper proposes an overview of the ongoing pilot campaign, detailing the three use cases under validation and the technical solutions developed in the scope of the project.

Index Terms—5G mobile communication; Network function virtualization; Smart Energy; Unmanned aerial vehicles; Demand Response.

I. INTRODUCTION

The NRG-5 (Enabling Smart Energy as a Service via 5G Mobile Network advances) [1] project has been funded by the European Commission within the framework of the 5G-PPP [2] to design and develop novel 5G solutions for the smart energy vertical. Indeed, the energy vertical represents one of the most demanding test cases for 5G, due to the highly demanding requirements across a variety of applications, such as stringent capacity for massive smart metering/AMI (Advanced Metering Infrastructure) services, and ultra-low latency for supervisory control and fault localization.

As of today, NRG-5 has analysed the smart energy requirements from a 5G standpoint [3] and proposed solutions towards an energy vertical oriented 5G architecture, providing a set of both general and specific purpose VNFs [4]. In this paper, the focus is placed on the validation of such results in realistic conditions. It is planned to conduct a campaign of tests on two different pilot sites, aiming at demonstrating the capabilities of the application of 5G technology in the energy sector.

II. FOCUS ON THE NRG-5 PILOT CAMPAIGN

The first pilot site is located in Terni (Italy) and jointly setup by ASM, the municipal operator for the electricity and gas distribution network in Terni, together with Emotion, a private company devoted to electric mobility. The Terni pilot site will validate two different use cases, namely the Advanced Metering Infrastructure as a Service (AMIIaaS), and the Dispatchable Demand Response as a Service (DDRaaS). The second pilot site is located in Stublach (UK) and provided

Fig. 1. Microgrid advanced operations enabled by NRG-5 in the Terni pilot.

by Storengy, an ENGIE company, European leader in the distribution, transportation and storage of natural gas. In the Stublach pilot site NRG-5 will evaluate predictive maintenance and incidents localization using drones backed by a 5G-like multi-RAT environment composed of cellular, satellite and IEEE 802.11 connectivity. In the following, we overview briefly the technical setup of both pilots.

A. Terni Pilot Setup

The pilot site in Terni is equipped with several branches of a low voltage power supply network and a set of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) generating a reverse power flow through a secondary MV/LV substation, thus requiring a matching energy consumption to avoid imbalances in the electricity grid. The surplus energy produced must be compensated via dynamic Demand-Response (DR) campaigns taking advantage of the recharge needs of electric vehicles. Furthermore, an advanced metering infrastructure is employed to monitor in real-time the power network optimization. As broadly illustrated in Fig. 1, the site consists of the following energy-related components:

- Two Photovoltaic (PV) arrays (180 kWp and 60 kWp), connected to the LV network;
- A 72 kWh Li-ion battery energy storage providing the electric power storage and supply services. It plays an important role in providing the required flexibility for DR campaigns acting as *primary reserve*, and executing dynamic *reactive power control* and *reactive power compensation*;

Fig. 2. Predictive maintenance as a Service architecture enabled by NRG-5 in the Stublach pilot.

- A 4,050m² three-storey office building, a 2,790m² single-storey building consisting of the ASM technical offices, data centre, operation control centre, and warehouse. The typical load varies between 50 kW and 90 kW with peaks ranging between 120 and 170 kW;
- Three smart charging stations (two SpotLink EVO and one Efacec QC45) and six electric vehicles (four Renault ZOE and two Nissan LEAF).

This energy infrastructure is enhanced by an innovative metering system, made up of new generation smart meters (5G-NORM [5]) and low cost Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) [6] able to collect real time data from the most crucial points of the district and transmit the data using the cellular connectivity (5G or Wi-Fi). The site setup is completed by general purpose servers capable of running the NRG-5 stack and in charge of monitoring and controlling the local energy exchange.

B. Stublach Pilot Setup

The Stublach Gas Storage Facility is located near the town of Northwich (UK). Gas is withdrawn from the national transmission system and stored over 500 metres below the surface in salt caverns until it is required by customers. A gas compression station is also located on the Stublach site to move the gas in and out of the caverns. Drones are already employed in the site for day-to-day activities, such as detecting early failures in equipment via aerial surveys, minimizing the risks incurred by humans during interventions in sensitive areas.

The objective of the test campaign is to perform real-time video analysis via semi-automatic flying drones to extract risks and raise the associated alarms. A local instance of the NRG-5 compliant Multi-access Edge Cloud (MEC) provides the local computing capabilities and wireless access. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the site consists of the following components:

- A custom built drone with HD Camera, capable of 30 min of flight, and controlled over a 2.4/5 GHz and 868 MHz RF controls;

- A *DJI Inspire* drone with a Thermal Imaging Camera FLIR XT, capable of 18 min of flight, and controlled over a 2.4/5.7 GHz band;
- A flight controller based on Pixhawk 2.1 [10], a flexible autopilot system intended primarily for manufacturers of commercial systems. The controller is based on the open FMUv3 hardware project of the Pixhawk project and runs PX4 [11] or ArduPilot [12] on the NuttX operating system;
- A local server with an Intel i7 8th gen CPU, Nvidia GTX 1060 6 GB GPU, SSD 512 GB, 16 GB DDR4 RAM, to run the local NRG-5 MEC instance;
- A remote server with an Intel i7 8th gen CPU, Nvidia GTX 1060 6 GB GPU, SSD 512 GB, 16 GB DDR4 RAM, to run the long-term predictive maintenance service;
- A Satellite ground station with a 1.2 m diameter Antenna, 6 W Block Up Converter (BUC), and an iDirect X7 modem.

III. NRG-5 USE CASES VALIDATION

Targeting the Smart Energy vertical market, NRG-5 has defined energy-specific use cases covering all three traffic classes as defined by ITU for 5G [7], namely massive broadband (xMBB), massive machine-type communication (mMTC), and ultra-reliable and low latency communication (URLLC). NRG-5 trials aim at exploring how disruptive concepts from 5G could be used in such energy-related use cases, defining also NFV concepts which would optimise the performance for 5G network in the upper layers to support business requirements of such use cases [3]. In the following, we detail how those use cases are validated in the NRG-5 pilots.

A. Advanced Metering Infrastructure as a Service (AMIaaS)

According to the future Smart Grid paradigm, customers will play a central role in energy flexibility, being equipped with components for decentralized energy generation and storage. In this context, smart metering devices will proliferate, offering far more complex capabilities than today, supporting real-time measurements, terminal auto-discovery and authorization. For security, cost, and operational reasons, however, a full implementation of the above features is impractical on the device itself, thus the assistance of the communication infrastructure is required. On the other hand, self-discovery and auto configuration capabilities enable customers to avoid utilities lock-in.

Real time awareness of the Operators: With the expected high penetration of Distributed Generations (DG) in the urban and suburban areas, Distribution System Operators (DSOs) require reliable technologies to control in real time the electrical parameters of their networks, enabling them to discover in time the existence of abnormal conditions, outages, and to perform thorough analysis on existing problems. The AMIaaS use case, backed by 5G technologies, enables a prompt identification of critical situations, e.g., when voltage is approaching the limits

TABLE I
LIST OF THE VNFs DEVELOPED IN NRG-5 FOR THE DIFFERENT USE CASES.

Acronym	Name	Description	Use Case(s)
vMCM	virtual Machine-Cloud-Machine	Provide access to data to applications either via local virtual twins or data hub functionality in the cloud.	AMIaaS, DDRaaS
vMME	virtual Mobility Management Entity	Provide UE location awareness and device traceability.	AMIaaS, PMaaS
vAAA	virtual Authentication, Authorization, Accounting	Provision services related to authentication, authorization and accounting purposes.	AMIaaS, DDRaaS, PMaaS
vBCP	virtual BlockChain Processing	Provide access to other VNFs, devices and third-parties to the NRG-5 blockchain infrastructure.	AMIaaS, DDRaaS, PMaaS
vESR	virtual Electric Substation and Rerouting	Incorporate logic to control the power flow in an electric Substation.	DDRaaS
vRES	virtualized Renewables Energy Resource	Abstract the monitoring and control operations of RES.	DDRaaS
vDES	Virtual Distributed Energy Storage	Aggregate location-based information about electric storage capacity and handle requests for increasing the stored energy.	DDRaaS
vPMU	virtual Phasor Measurement Unit	Handle and manage real -world PMU values to assess the microgrid health.	AMIaaS, DDRaaS
vMPA	virtual Media Processing & Analysis	Process in real-time a streamed video to detect and classify anomalies.	PMaaS
vDFC	virtual Drone Flight Control	Automatically control the flight of a drone.	PMaaS

Fig. 3. Power flow before and after RES integration.

Fig. 4. AMIaaS network service composition.

in some parts of the electrical network. The scenario under evaluation aims to evaluate the following KPIs:

- 1) the capability of the NRG-5 framework to exploit the near real time smart meter data provision;
- 2) the capability of a 5G-backed infrastructure to support real time analytics (e.g., data processing) and visualisation.

Real time visualization of trusted information by means of Blockchain Processing: A distributed sensing infrastructure based on PMU and 5G-NORM devices will increase the awareness of the DSO about network status. On the other hand, tampered data flowing from these devices could have

dramatic consequences. In this respect, the AMIaaS is going to test the use of a Blockchain as a means to guarantee the trustiness and incorruptibility of the data sent by local consumers and/or prosumers [8]. Indeed, this scenario aims to evaluate the following operational KPIs:

- 1) the capability of the NRG-5 framework to exploit Blockchain processing over near real-time data provisioned by smart meters;
- 2) the increased need of computing resources devoted to the NRG-5 framework.

AMIaaS Software Catalog: The AMIaaS network service, is instantiated locally exploiting the MEC concepts, orchestrated by an Open Source MANO (OSM) [9] following the service composition recipe detailed in Fig. 4, using OpenStack as Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM). Table I provides a description of the VNFs composing the AMIaaS network service, namely vMCM, vMME, vBCP, vAAA, and vPMU.

Functional and not functional evaluation plans: In the context of AMIaaS, the evaluation of the following topics is carried out: 1) deployment and validation of the AMIaaS network service on the Terni pilot site computing infrastructure; 2) deployment of 10 new 5G-NORM prototypes in the Terni pilot site feeding the AMIaaS with real time data; 3)

validation of mMTC communications, including operations such as self-discovery and self-organization of devices in the NRG-5 system in realistic deployment conditions; 4) evaluation of the delay incurred due to the decentralized verification of the Blockchain in order to provide a secure data storage and retrieval; 5) comparison of the developed solution against commercial smart meters (e.g., Lennt and ZMD405 of Landys + Gyr) installed in the grid, with respect to both communication channel (PLC, GPRS) and data size and frequency of communication; notably, the monthly data flow is expected to increase up to 1 GB/user (against some MB today) as well as the frequency of data sending could be decrease up to 20 ms (instead of 15 min today).

B. Dispatchable Demand Response as a Service (DDRaaS)

As depicted in Fig. 3a, without Distributed Energy Resource (DER), (including storage, renewable generation and movable load/storage as EVs) the power flow would be unidirectional. The power generated in large power plants would be transferred via high voltage transmission lines, then transformed into medium and low voltage (MV/LV) finally reaching the end users. Today, with the integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) (Fig. 3b), the power flow has become bi-directional. At the edge of the electrical network, where users are usually located, now there are production plants, such as photovoltaic or wind turbines, generating intermittent energy. Often, the energy produced there is not consumed locally, creating the phenomenon of reverse power flow that can cause grid instability and safety problems, such as thermal limit violations, overvoltage at remote nodes, frequency imbalance and fault equipment tripping. For this reason, more and more DR campaigns are being experimented, with the aim of instantaneously consuming locally the energy produced from DERs.

Energy flexibility to avoid voltage violations with high penetration of distributed generation: The underlying concept is to test the ability to balance the intermittent power generation of renewable energy sources with the use of DR campaigns using load consumption and storage composed of 2nd life batteries and through the control of EV charging. The 5G infrastructure, as instantiated by NRG-5 helps alleviating sudden voltage peaks via the control of the MV feeder to avoid voltage rise with the control running in a local NRG-5 powered MEC (in the form of virtual appliance). The scope of this evaluation test is to assess the performance of the NRG-5 exploiting the synergy between the energy VNFs that can model the real devices to address the new requirements capacity of the distribution network without the need of a grid expansion plan. In particular, this scenario aims at evaluating the following KPIs:

- 1) the capability of the NRG-5 framework to control the distributed energy storage, renewable sources and EVs;
- 2) the capability of NRG-5 DR mechanism to offer voltage support services to system operator under high DER deployment scenarios.

Fig. 5. DDRaaS network service composition.

Fig. 6. Custom built drone platform employed in PMaaS.

DDRaaS Software Catalog: Similarly to the AMIaaS trial software, running on local MEC, is orchestrated by OSM following the service composition detailed in Fig. 5, over an OpenStack VIM. Table I provides a description of the VNFs composing the DDRaaS network service, namely vMCM, vMME, vAAA, vBCP, vESR, vRES, vDES and vPMU.

C. Predictive Maintenance as a Service (PMaaS)

Predictive Maintenance of distributed generation plants, energy transmission, and distribution networks is an activity of utmost importance in achieving highest energy network reliability. Recently, the energy industry started to adopt manually driven UAVs/Drones to perform visual inspections. The challenge that NRG-5 faces is to offer remote flight control of drones (or swarms of drones) based on video analysis of drones cameras.

This use case tests the ability to stream an HD video from a drone to a client, performing image analysis on the go, as well as having the ability to control the drone (automatically or manually) to perform usual maintenance activities over an energy facility such the pilot site in in Stublach (UK). The NRG-5 approach focuses on the reduction of maintenance costs by allowing the reduction of deployment time, bringing down operational costs and avoiding accidents on site.

Functional and not functional evaluation plans: Three scenarios are tested on site. The first scenario involves the use of an autonomously flying drone to detect the differences between a typical image and what is seen in real time during its flight. The second scenario involves the detection and response of alarms (fire and gas detector triggered on site, access control

system detecting intrusion on fence, etc..), requiring most of the times the presence of an operator assessing the situation. This scenario involves the manual control of a drone to analyse the incident location so that reaction or decision making could be done faster. Finally, the third scenario tests the possibility of reaction in case of unavailability of a local team on site. A remotely-controlled drone is launched from an outer location to locate the incident and run the appropriate countermeasures.

Automatic survey inspection: In this scenario, operators receive live image analysis and alarms detection. As of today, site operators need to physically move to several spots to fly a drone capturing video images on a SD storage card for a later analysis when back to the office. This scenario helps performing routine activities in a much efficient way. In this context, the following KPIs are tested:

- 1) Coverage capabilities of the drone and its 5G link;
- 2) Deployment time of the network service, including the video analysis service, before a drone can flight - i.e., the time incurred between the request and the drone take off;
- 3) Evaluation of the false positive and false negative rates for the real time video processing services running on the NRG-5 instance.

Manual incident response: In case an alert is received by a sensor (e.g., flame detection) on the surveyed area, there is the need to deploy a drone inspecting the area to help taking the appropriate countermeasure. As a result, such scenario provides the operators with the possibility to analyse specific emergency incident occurring on site, by deploying drones faster than before. The following high-level KPIs are tested:

- 1) Deployment time of the network service, including the video analysis service, before a drone can flight - i.e., the time incurred between the request and the drone take off;
- 2) Time before the restoration of the incident by appropriately taking the right countermeasures after video analysis;

Remote control of drone via satellite: The final scenario gives the possibility for a maintenance team to perform incident response activities via a remotely controlled drone. Such scenario supposes that the usual communication to the site is not possible. The flexibility of 5G is exploited by remotely controlling the drone and by having the video images streamed to a remote location. For this purpose, the drone is piloted manually by an operator using a satellite link and available internet connectivity. In this case, the following high-level 5G KPIs are evaluated:

- 1) Run critical operation over different type of connection (Multi-RAT);
- 2) Bandwidth requirements for different video quality and drone speed;
- 3) Evaluate the false positive and false negative for the real time video processing algorithms running on VNFs.

PMaaS Software Catalog: The PMaaS trial software, running on a local MEC instance, is orchestrated by OSM following

Fig. 7. PMaaS network service composition.

the service composition detailed in Fig. 7, over an OpenStack VIM. Table I provides a description of the VNFs composing the DDRaaS network service, namely vMPA, vDFC, vMME, vAAA, and vBCP.

IV. CONCLUSION

The NRG-5 project has setup two test sites in Terni (Italy) and Stablach (UK) where the assets developed in the project are being tested in real-life situation. Both general and specific purpose VNFs have been developed and tested (e.g., Blockchain processing, Phasor measurement, Electricity rerouting, Access control, Mobility Management, Media Processing, Flight Control, etc.) along with network services matching energy-specific use cases such as AMIaaS, DDRaaS, and PMaaS. Also, core business performance indicators have been identified and will guide the validation agenda.

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REFERENCES

- [1] NRG-5, "Enabling Smart Energy as a Service via 5G Mobile Network advances", [online] <http://nrg5.eu>.
- [2] 5G Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP) Phase 2 projects, [online] <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-phase-2-projects>.
- [3] H2020 NRG-5 project, D1.1: Use Case scenarios analysis and 5G requirements, 2018.
- [4] H2020 NRG-5 project, D1.3: Final 5G Network Architecture to Support Smart Energy, 2018.
- [5] SUCCESS, H2020 project, [online] <http://success-energy.eu>.
- [6] M. Sanduleac, G. Lipari, A. Monti, A. Volukidis, G. Zanneto, A. Corsi, L. Toma, G. Fiorentino, D. Federenciu, "Next Generation Real-Time Smart Meters for ICT Based Assessment of Grid Data Inconsistencies", *Energies* 2017, 10(7), 857.
- [7] ITU-R, ITU-R M.[IMT-2020.TECH PERF REQ] - Minimum Requirements Related to Technical Performance for IMT-2020 Radio Interface(s), Report ITU-R M.2410-0, Nov. 2017.
- [8] Stephen Lacey, The Energy Blockchain: How Bitcoin Could Be a Catalyst for the Distributed Grid, February 26, 2016 [online] <http://www.greentechmedia.com/articles/read/the-energy-blockchain-could-bitcoin-be-a-catalyst-for-the-distributed-grid>.
- [9] "Open Source MANO website," [online]. Available: <https://osm.etsi.org/>.
- [10] Pixhawk 2.1, [online] <http://www.profinc.com/>.
- [11] PX4 Drone Autopilot, [online] <https://github.com/PX4/Firmware>.
- [12] ArduPilot Project, [online] <https://github.com/ArduPilot/ardupilot>.